

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Digital, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator "Individuals with basic or above basic overall digital skills in 2021 and 2023" and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Individuals with basic or above basic overall digital skills in 2021 and 2023 (in percent)

Note

Data for Albania (2023), Kosovo* and North Macedonia (2023) not available

Source

Eurostat, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tepsr_sp410/default/table?lang=en (accessed 6 February 2024).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Rapid transformative technological development for a competitive Western Balkans region
A Europe fit for the digital age

| | Development and linking of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) |
|-------------------------------|---|--|---|--|---|
| Albania | No new digital hubs created
No partnerships reported |
| Bosnia and Herzegovina | Increased number of hubs and partnerships |
| Kosovo* | No new digital hubs created
Information on partnerships not provided |
| Montenegro | No new digital hubs created
Information on partnerships not provided |
| North Macedonia | Increased number of hubs and partnerships |
| Serbia | No new hubs established
Increased number of partnerships |

Legend: Information not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Highlights

Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia have joined the Digital Europe Programme and can participate in calls for proposals

DIH are being established across the Western Balkans and increasing their operation, supported by the RCC programme capacity building for digital innovation hubs

